

Apparent Activation Energy of Oscillatory Chemical Reaction involving Cerium(III)-Acetonedicarboxylic Acid

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A tremendous upsurge of interest in homogenous oscillating chemical reactions has recently stemmed from the recognition of importance of feedback phenomenon¹. Oscillating reaction in aqueous media has been popularised as BZ reactions after its discoverer Belousov² and later by Zhabotinskii³ who studied oscillation in a number of organic acids having a common configuration, RCOCH₂COOH. Many investigators probed BZ reaction using different organic substrates, metal ion catalysts, inorganic acids and even reported oscillations in mixed substrate systems⁴⁻⁶. In continuation of our studies of oscillatory chemical reaction involving cerium coordinated acetonedicarboxylic acid as the organic substrate⁶, we report here, the value of apparent energy of activation of overall process. It has been long recognised that oscillatory system kinetics find its formulation in simultaneous set of different equations which derived from the application of Guldberg and Waage Vant Hoff law to the underlying elementary reaction steps. However, the qualitative feature of the system dynamics generally depends on relative values of different controlling strengths and not on exact magnitude. So it was thought in principle, if the detailed control characteristics and their parameters such as 'apparent activation energy' are evaluated, it would be possible⁷ to determine which of the number of mechanisms afforded, a realistic basis for experimental observations.

Results and Discussion

From the plots of time against the corresponding c.m.l. values, the oscillatory characteristics were calculated. 'Induction time' and 'time period for oscillation' were referred as t_m and t respectively, in the results (Table 1), showing the dependence of these on concentrations of organic substrate. The plot of inverse of t_m against concentration of acetonedicar-

boxylic acid abbreviated as [Ac(COOH)₂] (regression coefficient = 0.1133) reveals a linear relationship,

$$t_m = A_1 [\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2]^{-1} + B_1 \quad (1)$$

where A_1 and B_1 are arbitrary constants. This result is also in agreement with the dependence of induction period on concentration of organic substrate observed by Field *et al.*⁵. The result can be comprehended on the basis of the following virtually irreversible overall process (A),

As the experimental systems do not contain any bromide, the bromide consumption process (A) has to wait till there is sufficient accumulation of bromide through proceedings of processes (B) and (C). This explains the lapse of time referred to as t_m before the onset of oscillations,

Consequently, the dependence of t_m may be taken as the measure of average velocity of the reaction leading to oscillations. This leads to relation (2),

$$\text{Rate} \propto Kc_1 \propto 1/t_m \quad (2)$$

Similar dependence of [Ac(COOH)₂] on time period of oscillation at constant temperature is seen leading to equation (3) by a plot of time period versus inverse of concentration of substrate (regression coefficient = 0.1446),

$$t = A_2 [\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2]^{-1} + B_2 \quad (3)$$

This dependence is characterised by the decay of concentrations of oxybromine species as well as organic

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substrates via (B) and (C). The apparent rate of bromide consumption becomes much less during this period of oscillatory phase as bromide is now produced by process (C) as well as consumed by process (A). Thus time period is related to rate constant as in equation (4),

$$\text{Rate} \propto K_{c2} \propto 1/t \quad (4)$$

From equations (3) and (4) it is obvious that $\log K_c$ can be replaced by $\log t_m^{-1}$ or $\log t^{-1}$.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF OSCILLATORY CHARACTERISTICS ON CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTRATE

$[KBrO_3] = 3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.5 \times 10^0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[Ce^{III}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = $299.0 \pm 0.05 \text{ K}$

Sl. no.	$[Ac(COOH)_2]$ mol dm ⁻³	$1/[Ac(COOH)_2]$ mol ⁻¹ dm ³	t_m s	t s
1	0.003 1	322.58	80	98
2	0.006 2	161.29	60	70
3	0.009 3	107.53	52	64
4	0.012 5	80.00	50	60

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF OSCILLATORY CHARACTERISTICS ON TEMPERATURE

$[Ac(COOH)_2] = [Ce^{III}] = 5.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[KBrO_3] = 3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.5 \times 10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Sl. no.	T K	$(1/T)$ K ⁻¹	t_m s	$\log(1/t_m)$	t s	$\log(1/t)$
1	293	0.003 413	254	-2.404 8	170	-2.230 5
2	299	0.003 344	205	-2.311 7	140	-2.146 1
3	306	0.003 258	165	-2.217 5	118	-2.071 9
4	313	0.003 195	141	-2.149 4	100	-2.000 0

The results (Table 2) of other set of experiments give the variation of oscillatory characteristics at various temperatures. Making use of these results and above conclusions (equations 1–4), figures were drawn showing rate of reaction varying exponentially with the rise of temperature. They indicate the validity of Arrhenius equation⁷. The value of apparent energy of activation obtained from the plot of $\log 1/t_m$ taken as $\log K_c$ versus inverse of absolute temperature was 23.9 kJ mol^{-1} , that from another similar plot in which $\log K_c$ is considered as $\log 1/t$ was 23.0 kJ mol^{-1} and their mean is calculated to be $23.45 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The corresponding value of E_a for BZ reaction involving malonic acid reported by Körös⁸ was 67 kJ mol^{-1} and by Field *et al.*⁵ was 49.4 kJ mol^{-1} , working at temperatures 278 and 316 K. The average activation energy for malic acid⁹ was reported to be 26 kJ mol^{-1} . Obviously

our value of E_a is lower than that found for other systems as the organic substrate is not the same. Other ingredients serving as oxidising agent and catalyst being the same, it may be said that acetonedicarboxylic acid is very reactive and can sufficiently be activated much easily to play its role in BZ reaction consuming relatively lesser energy.

Experimental

A stock solution (1.5 mol dm^{-3}) H_2SO_4 (E. Merck) was made in double-distilled water. The aqueous solutions of acetonedicarboxylic acid coordinated with Ce^{III} was prepared in H_2SO_4 as described elsewhere⁶. Other standard solutions of potassium bromate (Baker, analysed and found free of Br^-) and ceric ammonium nitrate (S. Merck) were also prepared in the same stock solution of H_2SO_4 . All reagents were of A.R. grade. The oscillations were followed using direct reading electronic digital potentiometer (Toshniwal NAINA) of 0.01 readability. A bright platinum wire dipped in pure mercury was employed as indicator electrode, coupled with standard calomel reference electrode connected through 10% (mass by volume) aqueous potassium nitrate salt bridge. The Ce^{III} coordinated complex isolated from neutral media was white crystalline solid (Found : Ce, 42.05; C, 18.00; S, 4.45; H, 12.1. $(CeC_3H_3O_3)_2SO_4$ calculated for : Ce, 42.17; C, 18.07; S, 4.82; H, 12.04%).

A requisite volume of acidic solution of Ce^{III} coordinated acetonedicarboxylic acid to give overall concentration of $5.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of each was taken in a cell equilibrated at a desired temperature (± 0.05) in a thermostat. The last ingredient (10 ml of $3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ potassium bromate solution) also equilibrated at cell temperature was then transferred to the cell. The solution was stirred continuously. The e.m.f. readings were recorded every 5 s till no fluctuations were observed for a long time. The measurements were made varying the concentration of the organic substrate at 299 K in one set of experiments, while in another, all parameters were kept the same in four different experiments at 293, 299, 303 and 313 K.

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